

Affective Meaning Integration in Design and its Influence on Product and Brand Evaluation

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Abstract

Previous research and theorizing in product design and consumer psychology testifies to the importance of unity or congruence among affective meanings connoted among elements in visual communications such as advertisements, product appearance and product packaging (e.g., Hekkert, 2006; Peracchio and Meyers-Levy, 2005; Van Rompay and Pruyn, in press). However, understanding of the processes whereby affective meaning congruence impacts consumer response is far from complete. In this paper, we propose a framework for understanding congruence effects in design based on recent studies addressing processing fluency. Moreover, we will distinguish between studies addressing congruence effects among strictly visual product features and congruence effects among affective meanings connoted by visual elements and textual elements such as brand slogans in advertising. In presenting the latter, the role of individual differences in information processing will be discussed and tested in an experimental study addressing effects of ‘advertising slogan-product shape’ congruence. Practical and managerial implications are discussed.

Conference theme: Brands and Consumption

Keywords: congruence, processing fluency, impression formation

Introduction

Long standing findings from design, art, and advertising research indicate that visual elements such as shape, color, logo and typeface are not only perceived in terms of their formal or technical properties, but also in terms of the symbolic or affective connotations they embody. With respect to the experience of art, for instance, the artist Wassily Kandinsky primarily discussed the basic elements of abstract painting (e.g., points, lines, planes, and their spatial orientation) in terms of their affective ‘sounds’, relating, for instance, the ‘above’ to *emancipation* and *freedom*, and the ‘below’ to *heaviness* and *constraint* (Kandinsky, 1926). In explaining such relations, Kandinsky proposed an artistic sensitivity, which he referred to as the artist’s ability to “feel the breathing of the still untouched plane” (Kandinsky, 1926, p. 116). Although the reception of affective meanings may indeed involve a heightened sensitivity, in modern times structural relations between visual-spatial elements and affective meanings have been well established and ‘scientific’ explanations for such relations have been provided.

In a recent study, for instance, Zhang, Feick, and Price (2006) showed that rounded logos are generally perceived as more *harmonious* and less *aggressive* than angular logos. In line with the writings of Rudolf Arnheim (1974), they accounted for this relation by arguing that, on a perceptual level, angular shapes represent a confrontation between a stimulus and its surroundings, hence the aggressiveness connotation, whereas rounded shapes present no such clash between stimulus and surroundings (Zhang et al., 2006). Likewise, Van Rompay, Hekkert, Saakes, and Russo (2005) demonstrated a relation between a product’s relative height and perceived *dominance*, explaining this finding in terms of the experiential given that being in a high position is associated with greater control (e.g., visual control over those below) or power (e.g., objects are easier to manipulate from above).

Insights in structural relations between visual elements and affective meanings are important, not in the least because a considerable number of studies have demonstrated the increasing importance of affective (product) meaning with respect to consumer decision-making and the formation of brand impressions (Bloch, 1995; Childers and Jass, 2002; Creusen and Schoormans, 2005). For instance, Creusen and Schoormans (2005) showed that, apart from bringing aesthetic delight, in the eyes of consumers the most important function of a product’s appearance is the portrayal of affective meanings.

However, stimuli such as works of art, products and advertisements usually incorporate a diversity of visual elements (e.g., shape, typeface and color), often embedded within a context

comprising additional non-visual elements (e.g., titles, brand slogans or product information) as well. Hence, apart from considering affective connotations portrayed by visual elements or design features in isolation, there is also the necessity to ensure that the meanings connoted across these different elements match or are congruent in terms of the underlying theme. Although design principles stressing unity or congruence among design elements are well established (e.g., Hekkert, 2006), controlled studies addressing such congruence effects on consumer response are scarce. In addition, research suggests that congruence effects may vary across people as the result of dispositional differences in information processing (e.g., Peracchio and Meyers-Levy, 2005). Hence, in this paper we will present a framework for understanding congruence effects, and report the results from an experimental study also taking into account consumer personality.

Congruence, Processing Fluency and Impression Formation

In understanding congruence effects and the general preference for congruence over incongruence or unity over disunity, recent theorizing on processing fluency is insightful. According to this account, stimuli that can be easily processed are generally evaluated in positive terms and inspire favorable attitudes (Lee and Labroo, 2004; Reber, Schwarz, and Winkielman, 2004). The basis for these effects relates to the fact that fluent processing is experienced as positive because it indicates a positive state of affairs in the world (Reber et al., 2004). A considerable body of research shows that this positive affect may be used as a cue in stimulus evaluations of various kinds. Zajonc (1968), for instance, showed that repeated exposures to nonsensical stimuli, e.g., Chinese characters presented to Western respondents, leads to increased liking (i.e., the ‘mere exposure’ effect). Recently, this effect has been explained in terms of processing fluency, i.e., with repeated exposures, stimuli can be more easily processed, hence the increased liking. Similarly, fluent stimuli are generally also experienced as more beautiful or (literally) pleasing to the senses than non-fluent stimuli (Reber et al., 2004). For instance, ‘gestalt’ patterns such as figure-ground contrast, symmetry and goodness-of-form allow for fluent processing (Reber et al., 2004), explaining preferences for stimulus configurations obeying gestalt principles in perceptual experience.

The proposal of the studies reviewed next holds that perceived congruence of affective meanings expressed through product features likewise facilitates processing, and therefore positively impacts evaluations of products and their corresponding brands. After all, when confronted with products, consumers face the task of integrating meanings connoted across

product elements into an overall impression. Arguably, products high in congruence facilitate impression formation, as opposed to products low in congruence (cf. Hekkert, 2006), explaining why congruent stimuli are preferred to incongruent stimuli.

To test this prediction, in a first series of studies, congruence effects among affective meanings portrayed by shape and typeface design of a fictitious brand of bottled water were tested (Van Rompay and Pruyn, in press). For instance, in one of our studies, two product shapes and two typeface variants were selected either connoting *masculinity* or *femininity*. By cross pairing the shape and typeface manipulations, four product variants were arrived at, either congruent in terms of the affective meanings connoted (for instance both shape and typeface connoting *masculinity*) or incongruent (shape connoting *masculinity* and typeface connoting *femininity* or vice versa). Results were in line with predictions by showing positive effects of shape-typeface congruence on aesthetic evaluations and value perceptions; congruent variants, as opposed to incongruent variants, were considered more attractive, and in turn elicited higher price expectations.

Visual-Text Congruence and Consumer Information Processing

Apart from visual elements, stimuli such as advertisements, product packaging and websites also comprise verbal elements such as brand slogans and product information; elements that should optimally convey the desired product qualities and related brand image. Similar to the processing of affective qualities portrayed by strictly visual product features, impression formation should also benefit from congruence among visual and textual elements. For instance, when exposed to an ad for a new brand, it is arguably less difficult for consumers to infer brand positioning and assess related product benefits when slogan and product appearance are congruent rather than incongruent in terms of the affective meanings connoted.

However, whereas affective connotations of visual elements are relatively automatically processed, verbal elements require, at least some, deliberate information processing for their meanings to be picked up. Research in consumer psychology indicates that there are considerable differences in the extent to which consumers engage in, and enjoy information processing, reflected in consumers' 'need for cognition' (Cacioppo and Petty, 1982). Thus whereas consumers high in need for cognition are likely to process (product and brand) information (e.g., communicated in advertisements) in a deliberate and extensive manner, consumers low in need for cognition generally process information less thoroughly and, hence, may not even note incongruencies (cf. Peracchio and Meyers-Levy, 2005). By consequence, the former should be more attuned and affected by incongruencies than the latter.

In order to test this prediction, in a recent study we manipulated affective meanings connoted by pictures of hotel facades and accompanying descriptions on a fictitious hotel-booking site (Van Rompay, De Vries, and Van Venrooij, 2007). Hotel pictures and hotel descriptions either connoted *coziness* or *modernity*. Again, the picture and description manipulations were crossed so as to arrive at web pages varying in terms of visual-text congruence. Apart from showing the expected overall positive effect of picture-text congruence on attitude formation (i.e., participants gave more positive evaluations of the hotels presented when product picture and hotel description portrayed congruent rather than incongruent meanings), subsequent analyses revealed that this positive congruence effect only appeared for participants high in need for cognition. In other words, these participants processed meanings connoted by both hotel picture and hotel descriptions (thereby noting picture-description incongruencies), whereas participants low in need for cognition refrained from thoroughly processing and integrating information conveyed by hotel picture and description.

Inspired by the relative neglect of individual differences in accounting for design influences on consumer experience, we further explored the consumer side of reported congruence research, crystallizing in the experimental study reported next. Central to this study is the observation that incongruence can be considered a type of information ambiguity. That is, when different elements (e.g., slogan and product appearance) pertaining to the same source (i.e., the brand) communicate incongruent meanings, they inspire ambiguity regarding the brand's identity. Interestingly, research in social psychology indicates that consumers vary in the extent to which they can tolerate ambiguity in everyday life, a trait referred to as the 'personal need for structure' (Neuberg and Newsom, 1993). In general, people high in need for structure display a strong aversion of ill-structured or ambiguous situations, and a longing for certainty and predictability.

Based on these insights, we expected that incongruencies among meanings connoted by product appearance and advertising slogan would be particularly distressing for participants high in need for structure and much less so for participants low in need for structure. In order to test this prediction, product shape and slogan in an ad for a fictitious brand of soft drinks either connoted *naturalness* or *artificiality*, crystallizing in a 2 (product shape: natural versus artificial) * 2 (advertising slogan: natural versus artificial) * 2 (personal need for structure: low versus high) between participants design.

Experiment

Participants and Procedure

Hundred and nine shoppers at a Dutch supermarket (45 male and 64 female; mean age: 42.73 years) participated in the experiment. Participants were told that they participated in an evaluation study exploring consumers' impressions of 'Flynt': a new (fictitious) brand of soft drinks. The questionnaire comprised two forms: the first form containing a version of the ad (representing the manipulations) and the dependent measures, the second form containing the items of the 'need for structure' scale. After completion of the questionnaire, participants were thanked for their cooperation and dismissed.

Stimulus Materials

Based on pretesting two product shapes were selected, one shape connoting *naturalness*, the other *artificiality*. The natural shape was perceived as more *natural* and less *artificial* than the artificial shape ($p < .01$). Similarly, two slogans were selected: "*Lemonade too delicious to ignore*" (the artificial variant) versus "*Natural and honest: pure enjoyment*" (the natural variant); the former rated as more *artificial* and less *natural* than the latter ($p < .01$). By cross pairing the two slogans with the two product shapes, four ad variants were arrived at (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Stimuli used in the experiment (From left to right: *artificial* shape and *artificial* slogan; *artificial* shape and *natural* slogan; *natural* shape and *natural* slogan; *natural* shape and *artificial* slogan).

Measures

Product Attitude. Participants' product attitude was measured by a scale comprising three items reflecting the extent to which participants perceived the advertised product as *eye-catching*, *superior*, and of *high quality* ($\alpha = .89$). Participants indicated on 7-point scales to what extent they considered these items descriptive of the product.

Brand Evaluation. Similarly, brand evaluation was measured by a scale comprising four statements tapping participants' attitude towards the brand ("This brand appeals to me", "This is a fine brand", "I feel positive about this brand", and "This is an attractive brand"; $\alpha = .89$).

Personal Need for Structure. Participants' tolerance for information ambiguity was measured using the 'need for structure' scale (Neuberg and Newsom, 1993). The twelve items comprising this scale tap the extent to which participants can tolerate unexpected, unstructured and unpredictable people or situations as illustrated by statements such as "It upsets me to go into a situation without knowing what I can expect from it" and "I hate to be with people who are unpredictable" ($\alpha = .76$). Based on a median split ($Mdn = 4.25$), participants were scored as either low or high in need for structure.

Results

An analysis of variance with product shape (natural versus artificial), advertising slogan (natural versus artificial) and participants' need for structure (low versus high) as independent variables and the product attitude measure as dependent variable revealed non-significant main effects for advertising slogan, product shape, and need for structure (All F 's < 1). As expected, the interaction between product shape and advertising slogan was significant ($F(1, 101) = 13.13, p < .01$). Pairwise comparisons revealed that the ad with the natural advertising slogan triggered more positive product evaluations when paired with the natural shape ($M = 4.36; SD = 1.11$) rather than with the artificial shape ($M = 3.78; SD = 1.31$) ($F(1, 101) = 6.12, p < .02$). Similarly, the ad with the artificial slogan triggered more positive product evaluations when paired with the artificial shape ($M = 4.43; SD = 0.98$ versus $M = 3.51; SD = 1.33$) ($F(1, 101) = 7.04, p < .01$).

Most interestingly, the expected three-way interaction between advertising slogan, product shape and need for structure also reached significance ($F(1, 101) = 11.73, p < .01$),

indicating that the reported ‘product shape-advertising slogan’ interaction only applies to participants high in need for structure (see Figure 1). Inspection of means reveals no significant differences between congruent and incongruent variants for participants low in need for structure, whereas for participants high in need for structure, the ‘natural-slogan’ ad induced more positive product evaluations when paired with the natural shape ($M = 4.90$; $SD = 1.30$) compared to the artificial shape ($M = 3.15$; $SD = 1.30$) ($p < .01$). Likewise, the ‘artificial-slogan’ ad induced higher ratings when paired with the artificial product shape ($M = 4.65$; $SD = 1.06$ versus $M = 3.24$; $SD = 1.46$) ($p < .01$).

Figure 1: Three-way interaction between advertising slogan, product shape, and need for structure on *product attitude* (left = low need for structure; right = high need for structure).

Highly similar results were obtained for the brand evaluation measure. Again, non-significant main effects of product shape, advertising slogan, and need for structure were obtained (all F 's < 1). As expected, the interaction between product shape and advertising slogan was significant ($F(1, 101) = 11.30, p < .01$). Pairwise comparisons revealed that the ad with the natural slogan induced higher scores on brand evaluation when paired with the natural product shape ($M = 4.54$; $SD = 1.08$ versus $M = 3.81$; $SD = 1.31$) ($F(1, 101) = 8.77, p < .01$), whereas the ad with the artificial slogan induced (marginally) higher scores when paired with the artificial product shape ($M = 4.59$; $SD = 1.08$ versus $M = 3.96$; $SD = 1.29$) ($F(1, 101) = 3.17, p = .08$).

Again, the expected three-way interaction reached significance ($F(1, 101) = 10.07, p < .01$), indicating that the reported ‘product shape-advertising slogan’ interaction only applies to participants high in need for structure. Inspection of means reveals no significant differences between congruent and incongruent variants for participants low in need for structure, whereas

for participants high in need for structure, the ‘natural-slogan’ ad induced more positive brand evaluations when paired with the natural shape compared to the artificial shape ($M = 5.08$; $SD = 1.26$ versus $M = 3.11$; $SD = 1.03$) ($p < .01$). Likewise, the ‘artificial-slogan’ ad triggered higher ratings when paired with the artificial product shape ($M = 4.82$; $SD = 1.09$ versus $M = 3.85$; $SD = 1.30$) ($p < .02$).

These overall results provide strong evidence for the hypothesized congruence effects and testify to the importance of taking into account individual differences related to information processing.

General Discussion

The results reported confirm the importance of congruence among visual and verbal elements in visual communications such as product packaging and advertisements. Although we did not incorporate direct measures of processing fluency such as reaction times (Winkielman and Cacioppo, 2001), our results indicate that congruence facilitates impression formation, thereby positively affecting consumer responses. In addition to replicating congruence effects observed in previous studies (e.g., Van Rompay and Pruyn, in press), the results presented clarify the process whereby congruence affects consumer response. That is, by demonstrating that congruence effects are qualified by participants’ need for structure, the results reported confirm that incongruence can be considered a form of information ambiguity, the effects of which are thus dependent on consumers’ tolerance for ambiguity (i.e., need for structure).

Interestingly, advertising research indicates that incongruencies may be beneficial in low-involvement situations where consumer attention is generally low. In those cases, incongruence may be used as a means to attract attention and prompt elaborate rather than shallow processing (Heckler and Childers, 1992; Lee and Mason, 1999; Maheswaran and Chaiken, 1991; Meyers-Levy, Louie, and Curren, 1994). For instance, Heckler and Childers (1999) demonstrated positive effects of meaning incongruence on memory for ad elements, indicating that incongruence may indeed prompt elaborate processing by presenting a ‘puzzle to be solved’. Along similar lines, Ludden, Schifferstein, and Hekkert (2008) recently showed that incongruencies in product appearance (e.g., incongruencies among impressions elicited by visual and tactile aspects of product appearance) might be used as a strategy to elicit surprise. These overall findings suggest that congruence, similar to design laws or gestalt principles such as unity in variety and symmetry, give rise to aesthetic pleasure by facilitating processing,

whereas incongruence may positively impact consumer response by presenting something new or unexpected, and thus by disrupting background stimulus processing.

In sum, the desirability of congruence in design varies with the relative importance placed on attention drawing on the one hand, and (literally) pleasing the senses on the other. In addition to dispositional differences qualifying congruence effects, as demonstrated in this paper, differences in design expertise may also influence the extent to which consumers appreciate incongruencies in design. For instance, consumers with an interest in design may more readily appreciate a deviation from the usual or may be better equipped to interpret a perceived incongruence in design. Previous research indeed indicates that congruence effects are likely to vary depending on the availability of a meaningful context for the perceived incongruence (e.g., Lightfoot and Bullock, 1990). Of course, the availability of a meaningful context is not only a matter of design expertise, but is also influenced by what consumers come to learn about product and brand. For instance, an advertising campaign informing consumers that a new brand pursues an eccentric or unconventional brand image may render a perceived incongruence in product appearance interpretable, and may even boost, rather than harm, brand appreciation.

Apart from taking into consideration consumer characteristics, the overall findings presented indicate that design decisions should be informed by product type and the context in which the product is encountered. For instance, in cluttered retail environments, grabbing consumer attention is a prerequisite for purchase consideration, and therefore low-involvement consumer goods may benefit from (moderate) incongruent product packaging. However, when consumer attention is secured, e.g., when a product does not have to compete for attention or when consumer involvement is already high as in the case of high-involvement products, congruence might be best suited to delight consumers. Clearly, future research should assess the validity of these speculations.

Awaiting follow-up studies addressing these and related issues, in the meantime the results presented testify to the importance of careful consideration of visual and textual elements figuring in visual communications such as advertisements and product packaging. However, our findings also illustrate that it is the interaction between product and user that ultimately shapes consumer experience. Hence, in order to account for design influences on consumer response, insights in the minds and likes of those who are to use and consume products are of equal importance.

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